

Assessing constructed wetlands for water reuse in agricultural irrigation: a comparative study of treatment configurations

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ABSTRACT

Water scarcity is one of the most critical challenges for sustainable development, with agriculture being the most vulnerable sector. Constructed Wetlands (CWs) offer an efficient and sustainable solution for water reuse, enabling the treatment of wastewater to produce irrigation-quality water and reducing reliance on freshwater sources. However, treatment performance of CWs can vary and may in some cases be insufficient to meet the water quality standards for safe agricultural reuse. This study addresses this gap by evaluating and comparing the treatment performance of seven CWs types and their combinations, including both single-stage and hybrid systems, aiming to identify optimal configurations and assess their suitability for agricultural irrigation in compliance with European legislation. The CWs are located at the Experimental Centre for New Water Technologies in Carrión de los Céspedes (Seville, Spain). The results showed that the performance of CWs differed significantly among configurations. Significant differences were observed for TSS, TDS, BOD₅, COD and nitrogen-related parameters, while phosphorus removal showed no significant variation among systems. Hybrid combinations of CWs showed high performance for the removal of solids, organic matter, and pathogens. The results also showed that four out of the five CWs configurations complied with the regulatory limits for TSS and BOD₅, while only one system achieved the standard for *E. coli*. The hybrid configuration VSSF + FWS CWs was the only system to meet all thresholds for safe agricultural irrigation, with average effluent of 6.5 mg/l for TSS, 4.5 mg/l for BOD₅ and 3.3E+02 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*. Our findings show the potential of CWs, specially hybrid configuration, for wastewater treatment and safe agricultural water reuse.

1. Introduction

Water scarcity is one of the most pressing challenges for sustainable development in the 21st century [1,2]. It is a multidimensional issue characterized by three interrelated aspects: the physical shortage of water to meet demand; the level of infrastructure development that determines the capacity for water storage, distribution, and access; and the institutional effectiveness in managing and delivering essential water services [3]. According to the Global Risks Report 2025, water scarcity ranks among the top global risks, with severe consequences for ecosystems, economies, and societies [4–6]. Over four billion people face severe water scarcity for at least one month each year [5], underscoring the urgent need for innovative and sustainable approaches to

water management.

Water scarcity is primarily caused by a combination of human activities and natural factors [1]. First, population growth is a major driver of increased water consumption, especially in agriculture, industry and urban use [8,6]. Global agricultural water demand is projected to increase by 19 %, and municipal and industrial water use is anticipated to rise by 50–70 % by 2050 [7]. Second, water pollution significantly exacerbates water scarcity by reducing the availability of freshwater resources. This pollution originates from multiple sources, including agricultural runoff, untreated domestic wastewater, and industrial discharges [8–10,14]. Third, climate change is disrupting the global water cycle, altering precipitation and temperature patterns and directly affecting water availability and quality, increasing the frequency and

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severity of droughts and floods, and raising the risk of prolonged and extreme drought events [11,12,17]. Lastly, agricultural production is responsible of nearly 70 % of global freshwater withdrawals, mostly for irrigation [13,14], making it the most water-intensive sector and a major contributor to freshwater scarcity [15]. At the same time, it is also the most vulnerable sector and is expected to suffer the most from water scarcity [6,16,21]. More than 40 % of global agricultural production currently depends on unsustainable groundwater extraction placing long-term water availability at serious risk [22]. In this context, sustainable solutions are urgently needed to support resilient agricultural practices, protect natural resources, and address the growing challenge of water scarcity. Among the available strategies, water reuse, such as the treatment of wastewater to produce irrigation-quality water, has emerged as a particularly promising approach to reduce dependence on freshwater sources and enhance the resilience of agricultural systems [8]. By diverting treated effluents away from natural ecosystems and into productive reuse, this strategy not only helps bridge the water demand–supply gap but also supports the development of a circular water economy through a reliable and environmentally responsible alternative to conventional sources. Translating this potential into practice, however, demands coordinated efforts to overcome key technical, environmental, and socio-institutional constraints. For example, while water treatment and reuse schemes can offer a safe and stable supply for agricultural production [17], they also raise valid concerns about potential health and environmental risks, particularly due to residual contaminants such as salts, heavy metals, and pathogens [18,25]. Furthermore, the lack of comprehensive regulatory frameworks, along with administrative and governance barriers, remain key challenges to the widespread implementation of water reuse. These systemic obstacles are often underlined by critical gaps, such as the absence of an integrated global vision that includes all the actors (from reclaimed water producers to end users) and the need to develop risk management plans that clearly define responsibilities across the entire reuse chain. Finally, the broader adoption of water reuse also depends on the ability to adapt and harmonize water quality standards, ensuring safety and consistency across diverse regulatory and operational contexts [19]. In Europe, this need for harmonization is addressed by the EU Regulation 2020/741 and the European Directive 2024/3019, which regulate the use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation and sets out minimum requirements to ensure the safe and effective reuse of water. In particular, Regulation (EU) 2020/741 defines quality classes for agricultural reuse; for Class C, reclaimed water must meet thresholds of 35 mg L⁻¹ for TSS, 25 mg L⁻¹ for BOD₅, and 1000 CFU/100 mL for *Escherichia coli* [20,21,29,30]. Additionally, in the context of agricultural water reuse, nutrient concentrations must remain within ranges compatible with crop requirements while avoiding environmental risks.

To fully harness the potential of water reuse in agriculture, it is essential to adopt wastewater treatment solutions that are not only effective but also aligned with sustainability and resilience goals. Among the technologies supporting water reuse for agriculture, Constructed Wetlands (CWs) stand out as efficient Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for treating both domestic and agricultural wastewater, simultaneously delivering environmental, economic, and social co-benefits [22,23]. CWs remove pollutants through a combination of physical, chemical, and biological processes [24], and can be classified into three main types based on their design and water flow characteristics: (i) Free water surface flow constructed wetlands (FWS CWs); (ii) Sub-surface flow constructed wetlands (SSF CWs), which are further divided into vertical flow (VF) CWs and horizontal flow (HF) CWs; and (iii) Floating treatment wetlands. Additionally, different CWs can also be combined to form hybrid systems [24–26]. CWs improve water quality and effectively remove nutrients such as nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), reduce total suspended solids (TSS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and pathogens, producing effluent suitable for irrigation [27]. By providing an alternative water source, CWs support crop production while reducing reliance on traditional water supplies and rainfall, thus contributing to

climate change adaptation. They also protect aquatic ecosystems by reducing pollution and limiting freshwater extraction for irrigation [28–31]. Furthermore, CWs align with circular economy principles by enabling water reuse, nutrient recovery, reduced reliance on synthetic fertilizers, and potential energy and biomass production [31]. However, the implementation of CWs for agricultural water reuse continues to face technical and operational challenges [41]. The treatment performance of CWs can vary considerably depending on system design, influent characteristics, and local environmental conditions, and may in some cases be insufficient to meet the water quality standards required for safe agricultural reuse [32]. Among the operational challenges, bed clogging is another frequent concern, especially in systems receiving high loads of organic matter and suspended solids, as it can lower treatment efficiency and reduce system lifespan. Additionally, nitrogen removal efficiency is sometimes limited due to suboptimal conditions for nitrification and denitrification processes [33]. Alongside these operational challenges, there are also safety concerns. Pathogen removal is not always sufficient, often requiring complementary disinfection treatments or the use of chemical agents to meet reuse standards and in fact, the potential for CWs to serve as hotspots for antibiotic resistance has raised new environmental and public health questions more recently [34,35]. These limitations can be partially addressed by combining single CW into hybrid CWs, which usually show better performance than single CWs systems. When further coupled with complementary technologies the overall pollutant removal efficiency of these systems can be significantly improved [32]. However current evidence on pollutant removal performance in hybrid CWs remains limited. Further research is needed to understand how different system configurations influence both water quality outcomes and long-term operational sustainability, particularly across diverse agricultural settings [36].

In this study, we evaluated and compared the treatment performance of seven CWs types and their combinations to support the safe and effective use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation in line with European legislation. The selected systems are representative of the main CW designs and hybrid treatment trains commonly implemented in practice. Compared to previous studies that assess individual CWs configurations, we conducted a side-by-side comparison of seven treatment lines operating in parallel under identical influent characteristics and climatic conditions. This design enables a controlled evaluation of configuration-dependent performance, including regulatory compliance and agronomic suitability. We assessed their suitability based on pollutant removal efficiency and compliance with established water quality standards, aiming to identify optimal configurations that ensure both safety and sustainability in agricultural reuse. Specifically, we aimed to answer the following research questions: i) To what extent does CWs type influence on pollutant removal performance, due to differences in design and treatment mechanisms?; ii) Does Hybrid CWs result in higher overall performance, offering more robust and reliable treatment outcomes?; iii) How different CWs configuration perform in relation to regulatory thresholds for safe irrigation (specifically for nutrients, pathogens, suspended solids and organic matter). Our findings demonstrate the potential of CWs to meet water reuse standards, supporting their broader application and large-scale implementation as a sustainable solution to agricultural water management and water scarcity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site and context

Case Study is located in the Experimental Centre of New Water Technologies, in Carrión de los Céspedes, in Seville (Andalusia, Spain). It serves as a living lab for the collaborative development, testing, and evaluation of innovative solutions in the fields of water management, wastewater treatment, and circular economy. It also hosts numerous training activities involving a wide range of stakeholders. Covering a

current area of 4.1 hectares, the centre has several types of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for wastewater treatment.

The area is characterized by a hot-summer Mediterranean climate (Csa) according to the Köppen classification. In Carrión de los Céspedes, summers are short, hot, dry, and mostly clear, while winters are mild to cold and partly cloudy. The region faces several water-related challenges, particularly associated with seasonal drought and water scarcity, stored water quality, water pollution and runoff, diffuse pollution of aquifers by fertilisers, evaporation, and the effects of climate change. Agriculture is one of the main economic sectors in the area. Most of the agri-food activity is dedicated to rain-fed agriculture as sunflower and olive grove and irrigated agriculture as sunflower, olive grove and almonds.

2.2. Constructed wetland designs and configurations

A comparative assessment of seven different CWs configurations (see Fig. 1) were conducted at the pilot scale to evaluate removal efficiencies for both physicochemical and microbiological contaminants, aimed at wastewater treatment and irrigation reuse in compliance with relevant regulatory frameworks (European Directive 2024/3019 and EU Regulation 2020/741). Four of the seven CWs were fed with water from an Imhoff tank, previously subjected to preliminary treatment including screening, aerated grit removal, and grease separation. Their effluent fed two other CWs. Only one CWs received directly pre-treated water. The types of CWs monitored and evaluated included: Three Vertical Subsurface Flow (VSSF) CWs, one Horizontal Subsurface Flow (HSSF) CWs, one Free Water Surface (FWS) CWs, one Aerated-Intermittent Vertical-Horizontal (AIVH) CWs, one Floating Helophytes (FLH) wetland.

The CWs operated under various treatment configurations encompassing primary, secondary, and tertiary-hybrid treatment stages. The AIVH CW hybrid configuration functioned as a primary treatment unit. The VSSF-1 CW operated as secondary treatment, followed by the HSSF CW as tertiary treatment, together forming a hybrid system. The VSSF-2 CW operated independently as a secondary treatment unit. The VSSF-3 CW also provided secondary treatment complemented by the FWS CW functioning as tertiary treatment, forming another hybrid system. Finally, the FLH operates as a secondary treatment unit. Supplementary Table 1 summarizes the main operational and design characteristics of the evaluated CWs systems, including the mean values of the applied

hydraulic loading rates. Hydraulic loading rates were selected based on a balanced consideration of flow rate, pollutant loading, hydraulic retention time, wetland type, and local environmental conditions, aiming to ensure optimal treatment performance, hydraulic stability, and sustainable operation of each evaluated CW. The effluent treated through the seven previously described CWs is collected in a common chamber, from where it is conveyed to a storage lagoon for subsequent reclamation and reuse in olive grove irrigation. The hydraulic configuration of the treatment train was designed by combining gravity flow and pumped flow, according to the operational requirements of each unit. The different CWs configurations and the treatment train are shown in Fig. 2 and their location in the plant are shown in Supplementary Figure 1.

2.3. Monitoring and data collection

A rigorous monitoring and data collection protocol was established to ensure the optimal operation and regulatory compliance of the wastewater treated at the Case study. The program includes the water monitoring at inlet and outlet of treatment units with a biweekly periodicity. The monitoring period runs from October 2023 to July 2025. The water quality assessment parameters were selected based on multiple criteria: (i) compliance with the thresholds established in EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse for agricultural irrigation, specifically olive grove irrigation (Class C); (ii) the need to evaluate key nutrients for olive groves, namely nitrates and phosphates, present in reclaimed water; and (iii) additional parameters related to water quality at the discharge level. The assessed parameters include: pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), total nitrogen, Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN), ammoniacal nitrogen (N-NH₄⁺), Nitrate nitrogen (N-NO₃⁻), Total phosphorus, phosphate (PO₄³⁻), and *E. coli*. The corresponding reference methods for each parameter are detailed in Table 1.

Nutrient concentrations were evaluated against agronomic thresholds derived from olive grove nutrient uptake and typical irrigation demand. Based on Barranco et al [37], olive groves remove 54.4 kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and 6.87 kg P ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹; assuming an irrigation demand of 731 m³ ha⁻¹, these values correspond to concentration thresholds of 73.9 mg

Fig. 1. CWs evaluated in the Experimental Centre of New Water Technologies in Carrión de los Céspedes. A (Hybrid Configuration) - Aerated-Intermittent Vertical-Horizontal (AIVH) CW; B.1 + B.2 (Hybrid Configuration) - Vertical Subsurface Flow-1 (VSSF-1) + Horizontal Subsurface Flow (HSSF) CW; D.1 + D.2 (Hybrid Configuration) - Vertical Subsurface Flow-3 (VSSF-3) + Free Water Surface (FWS) CW; C - Vertical Subsurface Flow-2 (VSSF-2); E - Floating Helophytes (FLH) wetland.

Fig. 2. Overview of Constructed Wetlands configurations and Treatment Train at the Carrión de los Céspedes Case Study, including hydraulic layout. Light blue indicates primary treatment; medium blue corresponds to secondary treatment; and dark blue represents tertiary treatment.

Table 1
Evaluated water quality parameters, reference methods and applicable regulation.

PARAMETER	Unit	REFERENCE METHOD	Regulation
pH	-	S.M. 4500 H + B	-
EC	(µS/cm)	Standard Methods (S.M.) 2510 B	-
Temperature	°C	S.M. 2550 B	-
DO	mg/l	S.M. 4500-O G	-
TSS	mg/l	S.M. 2540 D	2020/741 91/271 2024/ 3019
TDS	mg/l	In situ multi-parameter measurements	-
BOD ₅	mg/l	S.M. 5210 D	2020/741 91/271 2024/ 3019
COD	mg/l	S.M. 5220 C, ISO6060–1989, DIN38409-H41-H44	91/271 2024/ 3019
Total nitrogen	mg/l	APC228/338, DR3900 methods	2024/ 3019
TKN	mg/l	EN ISO 11,905–1	-
N-NH ₄ ⁺	mg/l	Differential calculations (NT-N-NO ₃ -)	-
N-NH ₄ ⁺	mg/l	APC303, DR3900 methods	-
N-NO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	ISO 7150–1, DIN 38,406 E5–1	-
N-NO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	APC339, DR3900 methods	-
N-NO ₃ ⁻	mg/l	ISO 7890–1–2–1986, DIN 38,405 D9–2	-
Total phosphorus	mg/l	APC350, DR3900 methods	2024/ 3019
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/l	ISO 6878–1–1986, DIN 38,405 D11–4	-
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/l	APC350, DR3900 methods	-
P-PO ₄ ³⁻	mg/l	ISO 6878–1–1986, DIN 38,405 D11–4	-
<i>E. coli</i>	CFU/100 ml	S.M. 9222	2020/741

L⁻¹ for total nitrogen and 9.4 mg L⁻¹ for total phosphorus.

The treatment train was inspected on a weekly basis concerning the overall operation and maintenance. Major attention was given to the inlet flow to each treatment unit, which was checked twice a week.

2.4. Data analysis

All statistical analyses and visualizations were conducted in R (version 4.5.0; R Core Team). Data wrangling and summarization were performed using the *dplyr* and *tidyr* packages (versions 1.1.4 and 1.3.1, respectively). Percentage removal (R) for each water quality parameter was calculated by comparing the concentration in the pre-treated influent water with that in the effluent of each constructed wetland. Equations:

$$R = 100 - \left(100 \times \frac{C_{influent}}{C_{effluent}} \right)$$

A different method was used for *E. coli*. The *E. coli* removal performance is expressed in terms of log removal value (LRV), calculated by comparing the concentration (CFU/100 mL) in the pre-treated influent water with that in the effluent of each constructed wetland, according to the equation:

$$LRV = \log (\text{influent concentration} / \text{effluent concentration})$$

Non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis tests were applied to evaluate differences in removal performance among CWs combinations, using the *stats* package (version 4.5.0). All figures were created with the *ggplot2* (version 3.5.2) and *ggpubr* (version 0.6.0) R packages, and Microsoft Excel (2019). For the final data analysis, outliers were retained for all parameters to avoid introducing subjective bias, as their causes could not be unequivocally identified. Mean values are therefore reported, with median values provided in Supplementary Table 2 to support robust interpretation. An exception was made for *E. coli* removal performance, for which non-representative outliers were excluded

following case-by-case review based on analytical cross-checks and CWs operational status.

3. Results

3.1. Comparative removal performance among CWs configurations

The study was designed to provide a comparative assessment of different CW configurations to address key challenges related to treatment performance and surface reduction for implementation. While differences in treatment role and influent characteristics are acknowledged, the comparison is intentionally framed to evaluate the relative and context-specific performance of each configuration.

The mean quality of the wastewater feeding the different treatment units during the study period is summarized as follows. The influent to the AIVH CW and the Imhoff tank presented concentrations of 183.3 mg/l for TSS, 251.2 mg/l for BOD₅, 68.3 mg/l for Total N, 7.1 mg/l for Total P, and 2E+06 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*. The VSSF-1, VSSF-2, VSSF-3, and FLH systems received wastewater with mean concentrations of 146.6 mg/l for TSS, 217.9 mg/l for BOD₅, 68.0 mg/l for Total N, 7.0 mg/l for Total P, and 7E+05 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*. Lower concentrations were observed in the influent to downstream units, including HSSF (43.1 mg/l for TSS; 35.6 mg/l for BOD₅; 33.5 mg/l for Total N; 6.2 mg/l for Total P; 3E+04 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*) and FWS (35.4 mg/l for TSS; 35.5 mg/l for BOD₅; 35.3 mg/l for Total N; 6.0 mg/l for Total P; 1E+05 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*). Finally, the storage pond for irrigation presented mean values of 24.0 mg/l for TSS, 38.6 mg/l for BOD₅, 40.2 mg/l for Total N, 6.4 mg/l for Total P and 2E+05 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli*.

CW performance varied significantly across configurations (Table 2, $p < 0.01$ for all parameters), reflecting differences in design and system operability. Kruskal-Wallis tests detected statistically significant differences among combinations for TSS, TDS, BOD₅, COD, Total N, TKN, N-NH₄⁺, and N-NO₃⁻. No significant differences were observed for Total P ($p = 0.86$) or P-PO₄³⁻ ($p = 0.84$). Across the configurations, AIVH (A), HSSF (B.2), FWS (D.2) and FLH (E), exhibited consistently high removal efficiencies for organic and particulate pollutants. Supplementary Table 3 shows the percentage removal of each CW. Mean TSS removal in these configurations ranged between 92.3 % and 95.8 %, while BOD₅ removal typically exceeded 90 %. COD reductions followed similar trends, with most of these systems maintaining means above 80 %. Vertical systems acting as secondary treatments such as VSSF1 (B.1), VSSF2 (C) and VSSF3 (D.1) generally presented intermediate removal values and showed greater dispersion. Nutrient removal was more heterogeneous. Total nitrogen and ammoniacal nitrogen removal were highest in FWS (D.2), which also achieved the lowest dispersion in TKN reduction. Subsurface-flow systems displayed more variable results in nitrogen removal, with several combinations showing limited reductions or, in the case of N-NO₃⁻, negative mean values, suggesting oxidation processes that led to increase in nitrate concentrations at the outlet. Notably, FLH (E) was the only configuration with a positive mean

Table 2

Summary of Kruskal-Wallis test results per assessed parameter. P values were adjusted using the BH method.

Parameter	p-value	Significance
TSS (Total Suspended Solids)	< 0.01	***
TDS (Total Dissolved Solids)	< 0.01	***
BOD ₅ (Biochemical Oxygen Demand)	< 0.01	***
COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	< 0.01	***
Total N (Total Nitrogen)	< 0.01	***
TKN (Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen)	< 0.01	***
N-NH ₄ ⁺ (Ammoniacal Nitrogen)	< 0.01	***
N-NO ₃ ⁻ (Nitrate Nitrogen)	< 0.01	***
Total P (Total Phosphorus)	0.86	ns
P-PO ₄ ³⁻ (Phosphates)	0.84	ns
<i>E. coli</i>	< 0.01	****

nitrate removal across replicates. All other combinations exhibited negative means for this parameter, suggesting transformation processes that led to nitrate release or accumulation in the effluent. Phosphorus removal was generally low across all systems, with both Total P and PO₄³⁻ showing mean removal percentages near zero or below. The lack of statistically significant differences for these parameters ($p > 0.83$) suggests limited influence of CWs design and type of substrate on phosphorus dynamics under the tested conditions.

E. coli removal also varied across CW types, showing generally high efficiencies in all configurations but with distinct patterns among systems. Mean removal values exceeded 90 % in most CWs (Supplementary Table 2). The highest mean and lowest variability were observed in AIVH (A), achieving near-complete removal (mean \approx 97 %). Similarly, the FLH (E), FWS (D.2) maintained consistently high removals (mean \approx 96 %). This was followed by VSSF1 (B.1) and HSSF (B.2) systems, which also presented removals above 90 %. In contrast, vertical systems functioning as secondary treatment units - VSSF2 (C) and VSSF3 (D.1) - exhibited lowest mean removals between 84.3 % and 75.7 %. Although all CWs configurations achieved high bacterial removal rates, only the hybrid VSSF3 (D.1) + FWS (D.2) system achieved an overall average concentration < 1000 CFU/100 mL, fulfilling the reuse standards for irrigation, specifically for Class C according to EU Regulation 2020/741 on water reuse.

To assess the influence of the Imhoff tank on CW performance, removal efficiencies of the secondary-stage CW systems (VSSF-1, VSSF-2, VSSF-3 and FLH) for TSS and BOD₅ were calculated using two reference points: pre-treated wastewater (upstream the Imhoff tank) and Imhoff effluent (downstream) (see Supplementary Table 4). Removal efficiencies based on pre-treated wastewater reflect the combined effect of the Imhoff tank and CW units, whereas those based on Imhoff effluent represent the performance of the CW systems alone. Δ removal indicates the difference between both calculations. The comparison indicates that the Imhoff tank played a relevant role in TSS removal for the VSSF-2 system ($\Delta = 6.2$ %), while its contribution was negligible for VSSF-1 and VSSF-3 ($\Delta \approx 0$ %). In contrast, a negative Δ value was observed for the FLH system ($\Delta = -8.3$ %). For BOD₅, the influence of the Imhoff tank was minimal across all CW configurations, with Δ values close to zero in all cases.

3.2. Performance of single-stage and hybrid CWs

Configurations combining multiple CWs types across different treatment stages exhibited a range of treatment efficiencies depending on the role and sequence of units involved (Fig. 3). Percentage removals are consistently calculated using the pre-treated influent as the reference. Therefore, results reported for tertiary units (i.e., HSSF (B2) and FWS (D2)) represent the cumulative performance of the corresponding hybrid systems (VSSF-1 + HSSF and VSSF-3 + FWS, respectively).

Systems corresponding to primary treatment only (represented by AIVH (A), which integrates vertical and horizontal subsurface flow with aeration) achieved consistently high removal of organic matter and solids, with mean reductions of 92 % for TSS, 94 % for BOD₅, and 86 % for COD. Nitrogen removal in this configuration was more moderate, with values around 68 % for Total N and 72 % for N-NH₄⁺, alongside a negative mean for N-NO₃⁻. Secondary-stage systems, such as VSSF-1 (B.1), VSSF-3 (D.1), and FLH (E), also demonstrated strong reductions in solids and organic pollutants (e.g., BOD₅ > 85 % in all cases), with varied nutrient performance. FLH, incorporating floating helophytes, was the only system to exhibit a positive mean nitrate removal, while VSSF-1 and VSSF-3 maintained high ammonium reductions. TDS removal in these secondary systems was inconsistent, ranging from net reduction in FLH to accumulation in others. Tertiary configurations, including HSSF (B.2) and FWS (D.2), operated as polishing stages downstream of vertical-flow CWs. HSSF showed balanced performance across most parameters, with TSS, BOD₅, and COD mean above 85 %, and nitrogen values in the mid-range. The FWS system recorded the

Fig. 3. Average removal efficiency for each assessed water quality parameter (mean ± standard deviation). The X-axis represents the constructed wetland configurations, while the Y-axis shows the percentage removal in the effluent relative to the pre-treated influent. The overall removal performance of the effluent from all constructed wetlands (All CWs (F)) is highlighted in orange.

highest means for Total N (≈94 %), TKN (≈96 %), and N-NH₄⁺ (≈98 %), though nitrate removal remained slightly negative. Despite being a surface-flow unit, FWS maintained high organic and solid removal comparable to that of subsurface systems.

For system-level contextualization, the full treatment train (F), which integrates all CWs outlets, is reported; as it represents the overall effluent quality under the real operational setup prior to storage and

reuse. The full treatment train (F) delivered consistently high removal for suspended solids and organic matter, with mean values of 85 % for TSS, 82 % for BOD₅, and 73 % for COD. However, its performance on nutrient parameters was not uniformly superior. Total N removal reached 40 %, while TKN and N-NH₄⁺ were around 41 % and 27 %, respectively. Nitrate reduction was negative, as in most other configurations, and phosphorus removal remained low.

Overall, hybrid configurations improved the consistency of performance in organics and solids removal, the expected cumulative benefit for nitrogen and phosphorus was not consistently observed. These results suggest that while hybrid CWs configurations can enhance treatment robustness for certain pollutants, nutrient removal remains sensitive to specific system types and biogeochemical interactions within each treatment stage.

E. coli was used to evaluate the disinfection efficiency of the treatment systems under evaluation. The overall removal performance varied depending on the treatment train configuration. Among the systems tested, the AIVH configuration showed the highest removal efficiency (97.0 %), followed closely by FLH (96.7 %) and the hybrid system VSSF-3 (D.1) + FWS (D.2), with 95.7 % removal. The hybrid system VSSF-1 (B.1) + HSSF (B.2) achieved an average disinfection efficiency of 91.3 %, while the VSSF-2 system showed the lowest performance, with 84.3 % *E. coli* removal.

3.3. Effluent quality and compliance with EU water reuse standards

The Regulation EU 2020/741 [20,21] defines a unified legal framework for agricultural water reuse. According to this regulation, reclaimed water is categorized into four quality classes, depending on the crop type, how the crop is consumed, and the likelihood of direct contact between the reclaimed water and the edible portion of the crop. In our study, we evaluate compliance with Class C requirements, which apply to crops consumed raw where edible part is produced above ground and is not in direct contact with reclaimed water, such as in the case of olive groves. The main water quality parameters and limits regulated under this framework for Class C are 35 mg/L for Total Suspended Solids (TSS), 25 mg/L for Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅), and 1000 CFU/100 ml for *E. coli* (*E. coli*). Fig. 4 shows the effluent average concentrations of the CWs configurations and compliance with EU regulation. For more information, consult Supplementary Table 5 and 6. It can be observed that all the CWs configuration except VSSF-2 complied with the TSS and BOD₅ threshold for class C in most or all

Fig. 4. Monthly average effluent concentrations of the assessed water quality parameters compared to the thresholds established by European regulations for agricultural water reuse.

monitored months. Notably, VSSF-3 + FWS CWs complied with the limit in all months, achieving the lowest average concentrations (6.5 mg/L for TSS and 4.5 mg/L for BOD₅). In contrast, the VSSF-2 CW was the only configuration that failed to consistently meet the Class C requirements, with an average TSS concentration of 41.8 mg/L and BOD₅ concentration of 59.2 mg/L, exceeding the allowed limit. Additionally, only VSSF-3 + FWS CWs configuration complied with the *E. coli* threshold for class C in almost all monitored months, achieving an average of 3.3E+02 CFU/100 mL. In turn, the rest of CWs configurations exceed the Class C requirements, achieving between 5.6E+03 CFU/100 mL and 1.6E+05 CFU/100 mL concentration in FLH (E) and VSSF-2 (C) CWs effluent respectively. The full treatment train (F) which integrated the outlets of all CWs achieved an average concentration of 1.7E+05 CFU/100 mL, not meeting the minimum sanitary quality requirement for olive-grove irrigation. Subsequently, within the framework of another experimental design, the effluent from all the CWs assessed was subjected to a reclamation treatment consisting of a storage lagoon, ultrasound, and pressure sand filtration, consistently fulfilling the regulatory requirement < 1000 CFU/100 mL for olive-grove irrigation. With respect to nutrients, we observed that all CWs configurations complied with the agronomic limits defined for olive groves (73.9 mg/L for Total N and 9.4 mg/L for Total P). Total Nitrogen concentrations ranged from 3.8 mg/L in the VSSF-3 + FWS CWs to 51.1 mg/L in the FLH system. Similarly, for Total Phosphorus, the CWs met the limits in all or most months, with concentrations ranging from 5.7 mg/L in the VSSF-1 + HSSF CWs to 6.8 mg/L in the VSSF-2 CW.

4. Discussion

In this study, we examined the performance of different constructed wetland configurations in the context of agricultural water reuse by analysing both pollutant removal efficiency and effluent concentrations. While current legislation requires compliance with only one of these criteria, considering both provided a more complete view of treatment performance and system behaviour. The analysis covered key physicochemical and microbiological parameters, including organic matter, nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), and *E. coli* concentration, allowing assessment of suitability for regulatory discharge and safe agricultural reuse.

Overall, differences among constructed wetland configurations were observed in the removal of organic matter and suspended solids. For TSS, BOD₅, and COD, the hybrid configuration VSSF-3 (D.1) + FWS (D.2) showed the highest removal efficiencies, followed by the hybrid systems VSSF-1 (B.1) + HSSF (B.2) and AIVH (A). All three configurations achieved removal percentages in line with the thresholds established by Directive (EU) 2024/3019. In contrast, the wetlands operating as secondary treatment units generally showed lower removal performance, with the exception of FLH (E), which met the thresholds for all three parameters, while VSSF-2 (C) complied only with BOD₅ requirements. In general, our results confirm that hybrid systems are particularly effective for the removal of organic and particulate pollutants. These results are consistent with values reported in the literature for hybrid systems, which typically achieve removal efficiencies of 87 %–99 % for TSS, 84 %–96 % for BOD₅, and 74 %–95 % for COD [38].

However, a different pattern was observed for both phosphorus and nitrogen removal efficiencies. Consistent with their strong performance in the removal of suspended solids and organic matter, the VSSF-3 + FWS configuration also showed the highest nitrogen removal efficiency (total N, TKN and NH₄⁺), in line with values reported in the literature [39], followed by the other hybrid systems, AIVH and VSSF-1 + HSSF, which reached similar nitrogen removal levels (≈72 %) and were also consistent with previous findings [40]. While previous studies reported positive nitrate (NO₃⁻) removal efficiencies, in our study, with the exception of the FLH system, nitrate (NO₃⁻) concentrations exhibited negative removal values, indicating oxidation processes that resulted in increased nitrate concentrations at the outlet. This behaviour is

consistent with the nitrification–denitrification dynamics typical of constructed wetlands, where vertical flow systems favour nitrification and the conversion of ammonium into nitrate [41,42]. Phosphorus removal was also generally low across all configurations, reflecting the limited capacity of constructed wetlands to remove phosphorus due to substrate saturation and the absence of strong biological or chemical removal pathways [43]. In our systems, the substrates were not specifically designed for phosphorus sorption. The choice of filling material can substantially influence phosphorus removal and its longevity; therefore, low phosphorus removal can potentially be intensified by using reactive media with higher sorption capacity or by incorporating a dedicated [44]. Given the reuse-oriented objective of this study, nutrient removal efficiency was not considered a primary performance indicator. Instead, nutrient concentrations in the treated effluents were evaluated to ensure they remained within agronomic thresholds compatible with safe agricultural reuse. In this context, moderate nutrient retention can represent an added value by contributing to crop nutrient supply, provided concentrations do not exceed environmentally safe levels.

The contribution of the Imhoff tank to the removal of suspended solids and organic matter was found to be significant only in the case of VSSF-2, while it was negligible for VSSF-1 and VSSF-3, and even negative for the FLH system. These negative Δ values suggest that, during certain periods, the Imhoff tank did not consistently reduce solids, likely due to episodic overloading, sludge resuspension, or operational disturbance, in line with previous studies [45].

Beyond physicochemical parameters, marked differences were also observed in the removal of *E. coli* bacteria across the evaluated configurations. The highest removal efficiency was achieved by the AIVH system despite operating as a primary treatment stage. This was closely followed by the FLH system and the hybrid system VSSF-3 (D.1) + FWS (D.2), consistent with values reported in previous literature [46,47]. In contrast, the VSSF-1 (B.1) + HSSF (B.2) configuration achieved lower removal performance, comparable to values reported by Masi and Martinuzzi (2007) for sequential subsurface-flow wetlands [57]. The non-vegetated VSSF-2 system showed more variable behaviour, likely driven by physical entrapment in the upper filter layer. These differences highlight the role of vegetation in fecal pathogen removal [48]. Indeed, the variation in *E. coli* removal efficiency across the different CWs configurations can be attributed to the complex interplay of physical, chemical, and biological processes that govern pathogen removal in wetlands [49,50].

Taken together, these differences in treatment performance have direct implications for the regulatory compliance and practical reuse of treated effluents in agriculture. The use of reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation is widely recognised as a viable and sustainable response to water scarcity, particularly under climate change scenarios. Additionally, from a reuse perspective, nutrients present in reclaimed water may represent an added value, contributing to reduced reliance on synthetic fertilisers and supporting circular economy principles through the recovery of finite nitrogen and phosphorus resources [51]. However, its implementation requires that reclaimed water consistently meets quality and safety standards to avoid risks to human health and the environment [61]. In this context, we assessed if effluent concentrations of TSS, BOD₅ and *E. coli* across the different CWs configurations comply with the thresholds established by EU Regulation 2020/741 for Class C reclaimed water intended for agricultural irrigation. In addition, concentrations of key nutrients (total N and total P) were evaluated in relation to crop-specific requirements. While the EU regulation does not set specific limits for nitrates or phosphates in reclaimed water, Directive (EU) 2024/3019 on urban wastewater treatment (Article 15) establishes that tertiary nutrient removal is not required when treated wastewater is reused exclusively for agricultural irrigation, provided that nutrient concentrations do not exceed crop demand and do not pose risks to human health or the environment. According to Barranco et al [37], nutrient concentrations were interpreted not as a treatment limitation, but in terms of their compatibility with agronomic needs and

regulatory compliance for safe reuse.

Under these regulatory and agronomic frameworks, clear differences were observed in the ability of the evaluated CWs configurations to meet reuse requirements. The VSSF-3 + FWS CWs configuration was the only system in this study that met the average requirements for Class C reclaimed water across all key parameters. Furthermore, even for TSS and BODs, this system also complied with the more stringent requirements of Class A, applicable to all food crops consumed raw where the edible part is in direct contact with reclaimed water and root crops consumed raw, for all irrigation methods. Therefore, the strong performance of the VSSF-3 + FWS CWs in meeting regulatory thresholds for pathogens, suspended solids, and nutrients supports our initial hypothesis and confirms its suitability as a reliable and efficient treatment configuration for safe agricultural water reuse. These results are consistent with the literature, which shows that hybrid CWs are more likely to consistently meet reclaimed water quality standards compared to single-stage systems [52].

Additionally, all CWs except VSSF-2 complied with the average Class C requirements for TSS and BODs. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that most CWs types perform well in reducing these parameters to levels appropriate for agricultural reuse [52]. However, achieving adequate *E. coli* concentrations in treated effluents remains a challenge. Apart from the hybrid VSSF-3 + FWS CWs, all other systems exceeded the permissible levels for safe agricultural reuse. This aligns with findings reported in the literature, where few CWs systems are able to achieve the required *E. coli* requirements without the application of additional disinfection processes [53,54]. Nevertheless, some enhanced or hybrid CWs systems have demonstrated the capacity to meet these standards. For instance, Andre-Martínez et al., 2017 [53] reported Class A compliance using an improved HSSF CWs, and other studies have shown that various types of hybrid CW can achieve *E. coli* levels acceptable for Class C water reuse [55–57]. For the main nutrients, all CWs configurations complied with the established thresholds, effectively recovering valuable nutrients without exceeding crop requirements or posing environmental risks. Although nutrient concentrations varied across CWs types, the reclaimed water alone did not fully meet the total nutrient demands for olive cultivation. Nevertheless, it supplied a significant proportion of those needs, thereby supporting the reduction in commercial fertilizer use as highlighted in the literature [58]. Overall, and based on the effluent concentrations of key parameters (TSS, BODs, *E. coli*, and nutrients) the VSSF-3 + FWS CWs system was the only configuration that met all regulatory thresholds for safe olive-grove irrigation, confirming its suitability for reuse as irrigation water. In contrast, the other CWs configurations fulfilled some but not all of the required parameters, limiting their suitability for irrigation use without complementary water reclamation treatments.

Taken together, these results indicate that while Hybrid CWs can enhance removal of certain parameters, compliance with reuse standards depends on configuration-specific performance rather than system complexity alone. The fact that only one configuration met all regulatory criteria under identical operational conditions highlights the importance of controlled, side-by-side evaluation. At the same time, regulatory compliance alone does not fully capture performance variability or operational robustness. Therefore, compliance outcomes were interpreted alongside removal efficiencies to provide a more comprehensive assessment of system performance. Nevertheless, compliance with regulatory thresholds remains a critical decision-making criterion for practitioners and end-users implementing wastewater reuse schemes, as it directly determines whether reclaimed water can be safely applied in irrigation systems [59]. These findings provide design-relevant evidence for practitioners and policymakers implementing CWs systems for agricultural reuse under EU regulatory frameworks.

Despite the insights provided by this study, some limitations should be acknowledged. The inability to consistently identify and exclude outliers across all monitored parameters may have influenced mean

values for certain variables. Future research should focus on systematically identifying the causes of these outliers to improve data reliability and strengthen the analysis. In addition, this study focused on conventional water quality parameters and did not address emerging contaminants, which are increasingly relevant for water reuse safety and long-term environmental sustainability. Incorporating these compounds into future monitoring schemes would enable a more comprehensive evaluation of reclaimed water quality. Finally, although nutrient concentrations were assessed in relation to crop requirements, the agronomic impacts of reclaimed water use on olive yield, soil fertility, and nutrient dynamics were not directly evaluated. Further field-based studies are needed to quantify these effects and to validate the long-term benefits of reclaimed water reuse for sustainable agriculture.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated the performance of seven CWs for safe agricultural water reuse, in alignment with current European and Spanish regulations. Our results revealed notable variability in treatment efficiency across the different CWs systems. Hybrid configurations generally outperformed single-stage systems in removing suspended solids, organic matter, and pathogens. Nutrient behaviour showed more heterogeneous patterns depending on CW type and operational conditions. Nutrient concentrations were evaluated in relation to agronomic suitability for irrigation, ensuring they remained within safe thresholds. The hybrid VSSF-3 + FWS configuration was the only system that consistently met all Class C parameters defined in Regulation (EU) 2020/741, while also remaining below safe thresholds for nitrogen and phosphorus specific to olive crop requirements. Furthermore, it achieved concentrations close to Class A standards for some parameters, highlighting its suitability for reuse without the need for additional treatment. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of CW, especially in hybrid configurations, as cost-effective and sustainable solutions for supporting water reuse in agriculture and contributing to circular water management.

Data availability

All data necessary to support the findings of this study are provided in the Supplementary Material.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Isabel Martín: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Raquel Marijuán:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Bárbara Díez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Khalid Fahd:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Nuria Fernández:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Sandra Rodríguez:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Guillermo Solís:** Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Raúl Sánchez:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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